

Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-Nitrophenols by Some Uni- and Polyvalent Cations and Anions vis-a-vis the Kinetics of the Electrode Reaction

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Suppression of polarographic negative maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols in borax-boric acid buffer of pH 7.1 has been attempted at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$ using some uni- and polyvalent cations and anions as suppressors. The electrode reactions of the nitrophenols have been found to be diffusion-controlled and irreversible in the presence of different amounts of these suppressors. The values of kinetic parameters (αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$) of irreversible electrode reactions of the nitrophenols have been calculated by Koutecky's method. Efficacies of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions in the suppression of the negative maxima of the nitrophenols have been determined on the basis of αn_a values. The ease of reduction of the three isomers at d.m.e. follows the order *o*-nitrophenol > *m*-nitrophenol > *p*-nitrophenol.

RECENTLY, Chandra *et al.*^{1,2} have studied the suppression of polarographic negative maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols by some ionic and non-ionic surfactants vis-a-vis the kinetics and mechanism of the electrode reaction. It has been concluded that all these surfactants suppress the maxima of the three nitrophenols and their electrode reactions are rendered increasingly more irreversible with increasing concentration of the surfactants beyond the stage of just suppression of the maxima. However, the suppression of these maxima by uni- and polyvalent cations and anions has not been attempted so far. It is therefore worthwhile to attempt the suppression of the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols by some uni- and polyvalent cations and anions vis-a-vis their effect on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of these depolarizers.

Experimental

o-, *m*- and *p*-Nitrophenols were B.D.H. products, and were recrystallized from ethanol before use. The other chemicals used were of B.D.H., A.R. grade. The concentration of each depolarizer (in 4% ethanolic solution) was maintained at $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$. Desired concentration of borax-boric acid buffer of pH 7.1 was added to the solution to be polarographed. NaNO_3 was used as a supporting electrolyte in each case and its optimum concentration was determined by trial so as to get well-defined maxima. This was $0.1 M$ in the case of *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols and $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M$ in the case of the *ortho* isomer. A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal PL 50) was used. All measurements were

carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Purified nitrogen was used for removing the dissolved oxygen. The potentials were measured against a saturated calomel electrode (SCE). The d.m.e. had the following capillary characteristics. For *o*-nitrophenol, $m = 3.12 \text{ mg/sec}$; $t = 2.40 \text{ sec}$; $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.47 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$ (in $4.0 \times 10^{-3} M \text{ NaNO}_3$, open circuit); for *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols, $m = 3.16 \text{ mg/sec}$; $t = 2.46 \text{ sec}$, $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.50 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/2}$ (in $0.1 M \text{ NaNO}_3$, open circuit); $h_{\text{corr}} = 36.2 \text{ cm}$.

The following uni- and polyvalent cations and anions have been used:

Cations (nitrate being the anion in each case): Na^+ , Ca^{2+} and Al^{3+} .

Anions (potassium being the cation in each case): I^- , CNS^- , oxalate²⁻ and citrate³⁻.

The number of electrons, n , involved in the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols was determined by millicoulometric method of DeVries and Kroon³. This gave the value of n equal to 6 for *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols and 4 for *m*-nitrophenol at pH 7.1. Having known the value of n , Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of D , the diffusion-coefficient of the three nitrophenols at the point of just suppression of the maxima and beyond it in presence of increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions. The potential-dependent rate constant, $k_{f,h}$, was calculated by Koutecky's method^{4,5}. The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{f,h}^0$, were calculated from the plots of $\log k_{f,h}$ vs $E_{d.e.}$. Throughout the measurements the current at the end of the drop (i.e., the maximum current) was recorded for the reasons given by Meites^{6(a)}.

Results and Discussion

The first kind polarographic maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols in borax-boric acid buffer of pH 7.1 for a given concentration ($1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$) of each depolarizer and at the same height of the mercury column ($h_{corr} = 36.2$ cm) appear at -0.68 , -0.72 and -0.74 V (vs SCE), respectively. These lie well on the negative side of the potential of the electrocapillary zero which is -0.32 V (vs SCE) under the same experimental conditions. Since the $E_{1/2}$ values of the three nitrophenols at 7.1 also lie on the negative side of the electrocapillary zero, the maxima

of these depolarizers are of negative polarity⁷. The relative heights of the maxima are in the order *m*-nitrophenol > *p*-nitrophenol > *o*-nitrophenol.

Effect of increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions on the maxima of o-, m- and p-nitrophenols :

The effect of increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions on the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols has been studied. The values of E_{max} and i_{max} have been presented in Table 1 for the cations and anions. It is seen that with the addition of uni- and polyvalent cations and

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AND KINETIC PARAMETERS FOR THE ELECTRODE REACTIONS OF *o*-, *m*- AND *p*-NITROPHENOLS (IN 4% ETHANOLIC SOLUTION) IN THE PRESENCE OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF UNI- AND POLYVALENT CATIONS AND ANIONS

[Ion]	$-E_{max}$ V (SCE)	$-E_{1/2}$ V (SCE)	i_{max} μA	i_d μA	Slope mV	$D \times 10^6$ cm ² /sec	αn_s	$k_{r,h}$ cm/sec
<i>o</i>-Nitrophenol								
0.0	0.68	—	35.70	—	—	—	—	—
Cations								
Na⁺								
2.00×10^{-3}	0.68	—	34.68	—	—	—	—	—
6.00×10^{-3}	0.62	—	33.66	—	—	—	—	—
1.20×10^{-2}	0.60	—	31.28	—	—	—	—	—
1.90×10^{-2}	0.60	—	28.22	—	—	—	—	—
2.00×10^{-2}	—	0.465	—	27.88	68	7.10	0.802	7.21×10^{-6}
2.00×10^{-1}	—	0.452	—	29.24	67	7.81	0.811	1.36×10^{-5}
5.00×10^{-1}	—	0.420	—	29.92	66	8.18	0.820	2.55×10^{-5}
Ca²⁺								
5.60×10^{-3}	—	0.460	—	29.92	63	8.18	0.868	8.56×10^{-6}
5.00×10^{-2}	—	0.420	—	30.90	61	8.72	0.903	9.46×10^{-6}
5.00×10^{-1}	—	0.405	—	26.86	60	6.59	0.912	4.34×10^{-5}
Al³⁺								
4.00×10^{-3}	—	0.380	—	28.90	60	7.63	0.905	1.10×10^{-5}
4.00×10^{-2}	—	0.365	—	29.58	59	7.99	0.917	4.75×10^{-5}
5.00×10^{-1}	—	0.325	—	31.28	58	8.94	0.931	6.99×10^{-5}
Anions								
I⁻								
8.00×10^{-3}	0.66	—	39.10	—	—	—	—	—
1.60×10^{-2}	0.65	—	36.72	—	—	—	—	—
2.80×10^{-2}	0.61	—	32.30	—	—	—	—	—
3.20×10^{-2}	0.60	—	30.94	—	—	—	—	—
3.60×10^{-2}	—	0.470	—	29.92	58	8.18	0.929	5.35×10^{-6}
10.00×10^{-1}	—	0.465	—	29.92	57	8.18	0.955	2.53×10^{-5}
15.00×10^{-1}	—	0.435	—	27.54	56	6.93	0.970	5.69×10^{-5}
CNS⁻								
1.90×10^{-2}	—	0.450	—	31.62	58	9.13	0.941	6.26×10^{-6}
20.00×10^{-1}	—	0.440	—	30.26	57	8.36	0.947	1.31×10^{-5}
40.00×10^{-1}	—	0.435	—	29.92	56	8.18	0.968	6.36×10^{-5}
Oxalate²⁻								
8.00×10^{-3}	—	0.470	—	27.54	68	6.93	0.801	1.16×10^{-6}
10.00×10^{-1}	—	0.467	—	26.52	67	6.42	0.809	4.19×10^{-6}
15.00×10^{-1}	—	0.462	—	25.50	66	5.94	0.826	8.20×10^{-6}
Citrate³⁻								
3.60×10^{-3}	—	0.455	—	27.20	66	6.76	0.818	4.19×10^{-6}
5.00×10^{-1}	—	0.440	—	25.50	63	5.94	0.862	6.81×10^{-6}
10.00×10^{-1}	—	0.425	—	25.16	59	5.78	0.924	9.82×10^{-6}
<i>m</i>-Nitrophenol								
0.0	0.72	—	56.44	—	—	—	—	—
Cations								
Na⁺								
0.50	0.72	—	54.40	—	—	—	—	—
2.00	0.72	—	50.32	—	—	—	—	—
3.50	0.70	—	36.04	—	—	—	—	—
5.00	0.68	—	22.10	—	—	—	—	—
5.25	—	0.495	—	21.76	67	9.50	0.812	4.78×10^{-7}
5.50	—	0.492	—	20.40	66	8.35	0.831	5.81×10^{-7}
5.75	—	0.485	—	19.72	63	7.80	0.862	6.90×10^{-7}

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(Table 1 Contd.)

Ca ²⁺									
*5.00	—	0.498	—	19.38	66	7.54	0.817	4.92 × 10 ⁻⁷	
5.25	—	0.490	—	17.34	64	6.08	0.851	6.97 × 10 ⁻⁷	
5.50	—	0.485	—	15.30	62	4.70	0.874	7.01 × 10 ⁻⁷	
Al ³⁺									
*0.29	—	0.440	—	22.10	61	9.80	0.882	1.58 × 10 ⁻⁶	
0.50	—	0.420	—	22.64	60	10.10	0.909	2.60 × 10 ⁻⁶	
0.75	—	0.410	—	22.78	58	10.41	0.929	3.25 × 10 ⁻⁶	
Anions									
I ⁻									
0.50	0.70	—	48.96	—	—	—	—	—	
2.00	0.68	—	37.74	—	—	—	—	—	
4.00	0.66	—	29.92	—	—	—	—	—	
4.80	0.64	—	22.10	—	—	—	—	—	
*5.00	—	0.585	—	21.76	62	9.50	0.874	3.46 × 10 ⁻⁷	
5.50	—	0.575	—	20.74	54	8.63	0.890	8.70 × 10 ⁻⁷	
6.00	—	0.572	—	19.72	53	7.80	0.894	3.80 × 10 ⁻⁶	
ONS ⁻									
*1.06	—	0.560	—	22.10	55	9.80	0.982	3.99 × 10 ⁻⁷	
2.00	—	0.540	—	21.76	54	9.50	0.989	9.70 × 10 ⁻⁷	
4.00	—	0.530	—	21.08	53	8.92	0.995	5.55 × 10 ⁻⁶	
Oxalate ²⁻									
*1.60	—	0.550	—	19.72	70	7.80	0.742	3.15 × 10 ⁻⁷	
1.70	—	0.545	—	18.70	65	7.02	0.762	4.18 × 10 ⁻⁷	
1.80	—	0.542	—	17.34	62	6.03	0.799	5.21 × 10 ⁻⁶	
Citrate ³⁻									
*1.50	—	0.572	—	18.70	65	7.02	0.778	3.39 × 10 ⁻⁷	
1.75	—	0.570	—	18.02	64	6.51	0.782	6.48 × 10 ⁻⁷	
2.00	—	0.562	—	17.68	63	6.27	0.792	3.53 × 10 ⁻⁷	
<i>p</i> -Nitrophenol									
0.0	0.74	—	54.40	—	—	—	—	—	
Cations									
Na ⁺									
1.00	0.71	—	50.32	—	—	—	—	—	
3.00	0.70	—	43.52	—	—	—	—	—	
5.00	0.67	—	34.68	—	—	—	—	—	
5.20	0.66	—	33.66	—	—	—	—	—	
*5.40	—	0.525	—	33.32	69	9.90	0.791	2.70 × 10 ⁻⁷	
5.75	—	0.505	—	32.30	68	9.30	0.796	6.44 × 10 ⁻⁷	
6.00	—	0.485	—	31.28	66	8.72	0.811	8.63 × 10 ⁻⁶	
Ca ²⁺									
*5.10	—	0.515	—	29.58	68	7.80	0.798	3.51 × 10 ⁻⁷	
5.25	—	0.500	—	31.62	67	8.92	0.807	8.59 × 10 ⁻⁶	
5.50	—	0.480	—	30.60	64	8.35	0.839	2.69 × 10 ⁻⁶	
Al ³⁺									
*11.00 × 10 ⁻¹	—	0.510	—	30.60	66	8.35	0.824	9.62 × 10 ⁻⁷	
12.50 × 10 ⁻¹	—	0.480	—	32.98	64	9.70	0.851	1.34 × 10 ⁻⁶	
15.00 × 10 ⁻¹	—	0.455	—	33.32	62	9.90	0.879	9.69 × 10 ⁻⁶	
Anions									
I ⁻									
6.25 × 10 ⁻³	0.72	—	45.56	—	—	—	—	—	
8.00 × 10 ⁻³	0.72	—	43.52	—	—	—	—	—	
1.00 × 10 ⁻¹	0.71	—	39.44	—	—	—	—	—	
1.25 × 10 ⁻¹	0.68	—	33.66	—	—	—	—	—	
*1.30 × 10 ⁻¹	—	0.515	—	33.32	62	9.90	0.869	2.16 × 10 ⁻⁷	
15.00 × 10 ⁻¹	—	0.482	—	31.96	61	9.11	0.884	7.18 × 10 ⁻⁷	
30.00 × 10 ⁻¹	—	0.460	—	29.24	60	7.62	0.892	2.24 × 10 ⁻⁶	
ONS ⁻									
*1.10	—	0.525	—	27.88	63	6.93	0.872	4.70 × 10 ⁻⁷	
2.00	—	0.510	—	31.28	62	8.72	0.878	7.98 × 10 ⁻⁷	
4.00	—	0.500	—	30.60	61	8.35	0.887	9.50 × 10 ⁻⁷	
Oxalate ²⁻									
*1.25	—	0.540	—	27.54	73	6.76	0.739	1.14 × 10 ⁻⁷	
1.50	—	0.525	—	26.52	72	6.27	0.749	5.80 × 10 ⁻⁷	
1.75	—	0.515	—	25.84	71	5.95	0.764	2.31 × 10 ⁻⁷	
Citrate ³⁻									
*9.00 × 10 ⁻³	—	0.570	—	28.56	69	7.27	0.782	1.32 × 10 ⁻⁷	
5.00 × 10 ⁻¹	—	0.565	—	27.20	68	6.60	0.790	7.01 × 10 ⁻⁷	
10.00 × 10 ⁻¹	—	0.540	—	26.52	67	6.27	0.806	8.14 × 10 ⁻⁷	

* The concentration at which the maxima get just suppressed.

anions the value of i_{\max} decreases and that of E_{\max} gets shifted to positive potentials with the increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions. This is in harmony with the view recently put by Singh *et al*⁹.

Diffusion-controlled nature of polarographic waves of o-, m- and p-nitrophenols :

After the suppression of the maxima by requisite amounts of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions, *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols yield, in each case, a well-defined wave at pH 7.1. Millicoulometric studies reveal that this corresponds to a 6-electron reduction process in the case of *o*- and *p*-nitrophenols while in the case of *m*-nitrophenols this corresponds to a 4-electrons reduction process. The wave-heights are diffusion-controlled as evidenced by the fact that plots of i_d vs $\sqrt{h_{\text{corr}}}$ are linear and pass through the origin.

Irreversibility of the electrode processes :

Various criteria for ascertaining the irreversibility of the polarographic reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols in the presence of increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions were applied. The slope values (Table 1) of log plots in each case are much larger than the theoretical values expected for a 4- and 6-electron reduction process. It follows from this that the polarographic reduction of the three nitrophenols is irreversible. Further, the theory of irreversible wave^{9,10} predicts that the current is independent of the pressure head of mercury at the foot of the wave and becomes diffusion-controlled at the top, varying linearly with $\sqrt{h_{\text{corr}}}$. This dependence of the current on $\sqrt{h_{\text{corr}}}$ at different stages of the wave was also studied and it was found that the current was independent of h_{corr} at the foot of the wave whereas it was proportional to $\sqrt{h_{\text{corr}}}$ at the plateau of the wave.

Influence of increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of o-, m- and p-nitrophenols :

The kinetic parameters, αn_a and $k_{t,h}^0$, of the electrode reactions of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols have been calculated in the presence of increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions by Koutecky's method from the plots of $\log k_{t,h}$ vs $E_{a.e.}$ and the values have been listed in Table 1. A perusal of the Table shows that the values of αn_a and $k_{t,h}^0$ for the electrode reactions of the three nitrophenols tend to increase with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions. This shows^{6(c)} that the reduction of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols at d.m.e. is rendered increasingly less irreversible with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions. A positive shift in $E_{1/2}$ (Table 1) with increasing concentrations of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions lends support to the above conclusion.

A comparison of $k_{t,h}^0$ values at the stage where maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols get just

suppressed by uni- and polyvalent cations and anions may give a quantitative estimation of the influence of these ions on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of the nitrophenols. From a perusal of Table 1 the following order of $k_{t,h}^0$ values in respect of various uni- and polyvalent cations and anions is obtained.

Thus, among the uni- and polyvalent cations it is Al^{3+} which suppresses the maxima of the nitrophenols with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reactions.

Thus, among the uni- and polyvalent anions it is CNS^- which suppresses the maxima of the nitrophenols with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reactions.

The order of $k_{t,h}^0$ values in respect of the electrode reactions of the three nitrophenols at the stage of just suppression of the maxima by uni- and polyvalent cations and anions is *o*-nitrophenol > *m*-nitrophenol > *p*-nitrophenol.

Thus, *o*-nitrophenol is the easiest to reduce at d.m.e. followed by *m*-nitrophenol and *p*-nitrophenol.

Relative efficacies of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions in the suppression of the maxima of o-, m- and p-nitrophenols on the basis of αn_a values :

At the stage where the maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols just disappear (marked by an asterisk in Table 1) the order of αn_a values signifies⁸ the extent to which the addition of uni- and polyvalent cations and anions renders the electrode reactions of the nitrophenols more irreversible from the position in the absence of these ions. In other words a cation or an anion for which αn_a has got a higher value at the point of just suppression of the maxima will be more effective with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electrode reactions of the three nitrophenols. On this basis the following order of relative efficacies of various uni- and polyvalent cations and anions has been established :

It is interesting to note that not only the uni- and polyvalent cations but also the anions suppress the negative maxima of *o*-, *m*- and *p*-nitrophenols and that their (cations and anions) efficacies follow the valency rule. However, I^- and CNS^- do not follow this generalisation. This may be attributed to the fact that both I^- and CNS^- are capillary active substances¹¹ and as such they are likely to be more effective in suppressing the maxima. Further, the order of efficacies found on the basis of molarity is identical with that obtained on the basis of αn_a values.

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